

Catalytic Effects of Some Cobalt (III) Complexes in the Reduction of Nitrobenzene and its Reduction Products with Borohydride.**

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Three cobalt(III) complexes, e.g., cobalt bisbiguanide, cobalt salen and cobalt macrocyclic schiff base, are found to have remarkable catalytic property in the reduction of nitrobenzene and its various reduction products with borohydride, and are comparable to vitamin B₁₂ and its *in vitro* model, cobalt bis-dimethylglyoxime complex. The catalysis is of general nature and is related to: (1) the ability of cobalt(III) ion to reduce to a lower oxidation state of cobalt, i.e., cobalt(I) or cobalt(III) hydride and (2) the weak interaction of cobalt(II) and strong interaction of cobalt(I) or hydride with the substrates. The catalytic reduction of nitrobenzene follow the direct path: nitrobenzene → nitrosobenzene → phenylhydroxylamine → aniline. The secondary reaction path through azoxybenzene, azobenzene and hydrazobenzene is restricted. The efficiency of the catalyst depends on the nature of coordination and the stability of the low oxidation state of the metal ion in the complex. While the nature of the reduced products and the product-yields depend on the complex in a complicated manner; for the formation of aniline the order is: salen > bigH > macrocyclic base (N₄), which may be modified or completely reversed for minor products. Effects of temperature, reaction time and pH of the solution are studied and these influence the reaction.

THE cobalt complexes with biguanide and related ligands show some characteristic reactions similar to the vitamin B₁₂ complexes¹. Particularly, the oxidation-reduction reactions, and the facility with which cobalt-carbon bonded compounds are formed, have led one to recognise the usefulness of cobalt bisbiguanide complexes as models of vitamin B₁₂ and its derivatives. Following our earlier qualitative observation that cobalt bisbiguanide complexes are effective catalysts in the borohydride reduction of some simple substrates², it has been considered worthwhile to look at the borohydride reduction of nitrobenzene, a reaction tried with such metal complex catalysts as vitamin B₁₂, cobalt tris-dipyridyl complex, etc., by earlier workers^{3,4}. In this paper it is attempted to evaluate the effectiveness of the different cobalt(III) complexes toward the

reduction reactions under varying experimental conditions. A tentative explanation is given for the reaction path and the role of catalyst.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Nitrobenzene, nitrosobenzene, hydrazobenzene, sodium borohydride, potassium borohydride, and vitamin B₁₂ are all B.D.H. chemicals. Azobenzene is of E. Merck quality. Nitrobenzene is distilled prior to use. Azoxybenzene and phenylhydroxylamine are prepared by following standard procedures. The complexes [Co(bigH)₂(OH)(H₂O)]SO₄ · 2H₂O; [Co(salen)(H₂O)₂]Cl; [Co(N₄)CO₃]ClO₄ and H[Co(dmgh)₂Cl₂] are prepared by following usual published procedures. The symbols used here are :

symbol	formula	symbol	name
Co(bigH) ₂	= [Co(bigH) ₂ ⁻ (OH)(H ₂ O)]SO ₄	(bigH)	= biguanide
Co(salen)	= [Co(salen)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	(salen)	= bis(salicylaldehyde)ethylenedimine
Co(N ₄)	= [Co(N ₄)CO ₃]ClO ₄	(N ₄)	= 5,7,7,12,14,14-hexamethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraaza-cyclotetradeca-4,11-diene
Co(dmgh) ₂	= [Co(dmgh) ₂ Cl ₂]H	(dmgh)	= dimethylglyoxime

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Procedure :

A known amount of the organic compound is added to a fixed volume (20 ml.) of alcohol-water (60 : 40) mixture placed in the reaction vessel followed by the addition of a known amount of the cobalt complex. A number of sets are made for different complexes and for different temperatures. The reaction solution is then flushed with nitrogen gas for about 15 minutes and then required amount of sodium or potassium borohydride is added gradually to the reaction mixture, little at a time, and covering a long period, keeping the reaction solution under nitrogen with constant stirring. The vessels are placed in the thermostat to maintain the constant reaction temperature ($\pm 1^\circ$) throughout the procedure. The reactions are allowed to proceed for a fixed period of time. Organic products from the solution are then rapidly extracted with solvent ether and dried by anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ether is then distilled off and the products obtained are ready for various analysis.

Analysis :

The reaction products are analysed by usual chemical procedures and by thin layer chromatography (t.l.c) on 'Kieselgel G. nach Stall' [MERCK quality for thin layer chromatography]. The absorption spectra (both uv and visible) of the products are also recorded along with the original pure compounds. The percentage of each of the products are correct with an error limit of $\pm 5\%$.

Results and Discussion

The general path for the reduction of nitrobenzene is

Another possibility is by the process

Formation of azobenzene may further be effected by the condensation of C_6H_5NO and $C_6H_5NH_2$, or by the process

The general pattern of the catalytic reduction appears to be the reduction of the nitrobenzene to one or more products ultimately producing aniline to different extent and it is the cobalt ion which is responsible for catalytic activity. Different products are formed to different

extent under varying experimental conditions which suggest that reaction time, reaction temperature, complex to borohydride ratio, nature of the complex, pH of the solution and nature of the solvent may be the controlling factors for the relative percentage of the products. At higher complex concentration the reaction proceeds within a shorter time⁴. As shown earlier⁵ nitrobenzene is not reduced by borohydride but instead gives a radical anion $(C_6H_5NO_2)^-$, although later it is noticed that small amount of azoxybenzene is formed depending on conditions.

All the available data on the reduction of nitrobenzene and its reduction-products, in presence of different catalysts under different experimental conditions, are tabulated in Table 1 and 2. From Table 1 it appears that the formation of aniline is about 50% (at 100°) while other products such as azoxybenzene, azobenzene are also formed to a lesser extent. Hydrazobenzene and phenylhydroxylamine are formed, if at all, in trace quantities. At higher temperature the percentage of aniline is increased. The catalyst also stabilises the intermediate products at high temperature, and the amount of azobenzene found remains more or less constant while that of azoxybenzene depends on the catalyst. In uncatalysed condition no aniline is formed, but azoxybenzene together with a little amount of azobenzene are obtained. During a shorter time period (6 hours) the possibility of side reactions would be minimised and one expects higher yields of the intermediate products at the cost of the final product, e.g., aniline. The percentage of azobenzene is nearly the same for all the catalysts and much higher. The percentage of azoxybenzene slightly varies with the complexes but remain at the same level as in the previous cases. The cationic part of BH_4^- has very little effect which is evidenced when $NaBH_4$ is replaced by KBH_4 . In acid medium (zinc-acetic acid) the blank shows the formation of aniline, azobenzene and azoxybenzene in significant amounts, but with complexes the percentage of aniline increases at the cost of azoxybenzene keeping the level of azobenzene nearly constant. This hints to a reaction mechanism of azoxybenzene to aniline perhaps without involving the formation of azobenzene but other products. In order to understand the reduction paths of the intermediates it is necessary to study the effect of catalyst on the reduction of each of the intermediate compounds. Under the experimental conditions both azobenzene and hydrazobenzene are unaffected forming no expected products with any one of the complexes. Such inertness towards chemical reduction with borohydride may account for the constant level of azobenzene in different reductions mentioned earlier. Apart from azoxybenzene, which only forms inactive azobenzene; nitrosobenzene and phenylhydroxylamine are found to form different intermediate products (Table 2). All these taken together leads one to the conclusion that of the two reaction paths, the path(1) is the more favourable one. The path (2) is either forbidden or is too a slow process to form the products to significant amounts. For the formation of aniline from nitrosobenzene and phenylhydroxylamine the Co(salen) complex is the most

TABLE 1—REDUCTION OF NITROBENZENE (0.6gm.) BY NaBH₄ (0.5gm.) IN ETHANOL-WATER (60:40)

Complex (0.02 gm)	temp°C	time in hour	aniline	products in azoxybenzene	percentage ⁺ azobenzene	hydrazobenzene
1. [Co(salen)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	100	24	60	8	20	—
	40	24	45	10	20	—
	40	6	22	10	45	2
2. [Co(bigH) ₂ (OH)(H ₂ O)]SO ₄	100	24	50	15	25	5
	40	24	42	10	25	8
	40	6	18	14	48	3
3. [Co(N ₄)CO ₃]ClO ₄	100	24	45	20	25	—
	40	24	40	15	20	2
	40	6	15	15	40	—
4. [Co(dmGH) ₂ Cl ₂] H	100	24	55	10	20	
5. Vitamin B ₁₂	100	24	56	15	20	—
6. Blank	100	24	—	15	8	—
	40	24	—	12	6	—
	40	6	—	10	5	—

TABLE 2—REDUCTION OF THE REDUCTION-PRODUCTS OF NITROBENZENE (0.6gm) WITH NaBH₄ (0.5gm) FOR 6 HOURS AT 60°C

Compound	Complex (0.02 gm)	aniline	products in azoxybenzene	percentage ⁺ azobenzene
Nitrosobenzene	[Co(salen)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	25	8	20
Nitrosobenzene	[Co(bigH) ₂ (OH)(H ₂ O)]SO ₄	20	5	18
Nitrosobenzene	[Co(N ₄)CO ₃]ClO ₄	18	5	15
Nitrosobenzene	Blank	—	22	5
Phenylhydroxyl-amine	[Co(salen)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	30	28	8
Phenylhydroxyl-amine	[Co(bigH)(OH)(H ₂ O)]SO ₄	25	28	10
Phenylhydroxyl-amine	[Co(N ₄)CO ₃]ClO ₄	26	25	5
Phenylhydroxyl-amine	Blank	20	—	12

⁺ unreacted starting materials are not included and percentage of total recovered material generally lies between 70-100% (approx.)

effective one. For aniline formation from nitrosobenzene at high temperature the general order is $\text{Co}(\text{salen}) > \text{Co}(\text{bigH})_2 > \text{Co}(\text{N}_4)$. The low catalytic property of the $\text{Co}(\text{N}_4)$ can be explained in terms of nonplanarity of the ring and non-availability of vacant coordination sites due to strongly bound carbonato group. In contrast with nitrobenzene the $\text{Co}(\text{N}_4)$ compound is favourable for the formation of azoxybenzene which means that as the conventional path for aniline formation is restricted, a tendency develops to take the alternative route [see the reduction scheme (1) and (2) for nitrobenzene]. However, any attempts to rationalise a general order for all types of reactions has its obvious limitations for each reactant has its own peculiarities.

The general nature of catalysis by cobalt complexes and the complexes studied can be accounted in terms of variable oxidation states of cobalt capable of existing in, and the stabilization of the low oxidation states of +2 or +1 in the complexes. It is now established that vitamin B_{12} , $\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{bigH})_2$ complexes all form fairly stable reduction products with borohydride, which correspond to a two electron reduction of the cobalt(III) complexes, either in the $\text{Co}(\text{I})$ or in the hydride, $\text{Co}(\text{III})\text{H}^-$ state. Thus it is probable that the catalytic reduction of nitrobenzene or any of its intermediate reduction products is a complicated process involving the reduction of the $\text{Co}(\text{III})$ complexes which instantly reacts with the substrate. From our studies with $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ (salen) and other related $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ complexes, we observe the formation of a deep red-brown colour indicating a very weak type of complex formation between nitrobenzene and the $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ complexes⁶. Such an intermediate complex formation may be necessary prior to the reduction of nitrobenzene by electron transfer from the cobalt (I) or H^- transfer from $\text{Co}(\text{III})\text{H}^-$. It is logical to suggest that the reduction of $\text{Co}(\text{III})$ by BH_4^- to $\text{Co}(\text{II})$ or even a lower oxidation state is a kinetically controlled slow process while the electron or H^- transfer is a very fast one. The ligand around the metal ion in the complexes may have some stereochemical effect for change of geometry and or influencing the electronic properties of the reduced complexes.

The tentative reaction path may be written as follows :

The former reaction should be the most favourable in alkaline solution as the reduced complex predominates in the cobalt (I) state.

2) Further conversion of nitrosobenzene to phenylhydroxylamine is also anticipated involving $\text{Co}(\text{I})$ on similar arguments,

3) The formation of aniline from phenylhydroxylamine can be by hydride transfer from the $\text{Co}(\text{III})\text{H}^-$ or by the $\text{Co}(\text{I})$ species.

In slightly acid or neutral medium the hydride transfer reaction is the most favourable one and $\text{Co}(\text{bigH})_2$ is a much better catalyst for the formation of aniline which is consistent with a hydride transfer reaction from cobalt biguanide hydride, which is the most stable hydride in the series.

In Table 1 are given some data for two other complexes, i.e., vitamin B_{12} and $\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2$. It appears, the three complexes studied are not basically different in simple catalytic properties from the two well studied systems.

References

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